

Economic Conditions of Agriculture Before & After Covid Extuation

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The COVID-19 pandemic has greatest devastating impact on the human health and global economy the world has faced after 2 world war. Like other sectors the food and agriculture sectors have also felt these effects. In many countries, the measures taken to control the spread of the virus were initiated to hamper the supply of agricultural products to markets and consumers inside and outside the borders. This pandemic has some deep impacts on food safety, nutrition, and the livelihoods of farmers, fishermen, and others working in the food supply chain depends mainly on short, medium, and long-term policy responses. The aim of the review paper is to highlight the valuable insight on the impact of COVID-19 on the Indian agricultural system and rural economy, as well as some potential strategies for post pandemic recovery.

Impact on Agriculture Production

The impact of lockdown imposed in the entire country owing to COVID 19 on the overall production levels in the agricultural and allied sector has been significant with overall production levels

Decrease in magnitude of production in Agri and allied sector in percentage

in the agriculture and allied sector declining in 47% in some districts. However, 19% of the districts have also reported an increase in the overall level of production in the sector and 34% of the districts have shown no change in the levels of production in the agriculture and the allied sector. Some of the reasons for decline in agricultural activities include lack of availability of labour and machines, need for social distancing, and restrictions on free movement of men and machineries.

Impact On Availability and Prices of Agri-Inputs

The overall availability of Agri-inputs was reported to have declined in 58% in some districts and 38% of the total districts surveyed reported no change in the availability of Agri-input, whereas only 4% districts reported an increase in the availability of Agri-inputs. The feedback on availability and prices of various Agri-inputs like seeds, fertilizers, pesticides, rentals agricultural machinery, fodder/cattle feed, etc, were obtained to gain greater insights into the agriculture sector during the lockdown period. There is an overall magnitude of change in the availability of the Agri-inputs in each category. The aggregate availability of Agri-inputs at national level was reported to have declined across all subsectors. The highest decline was in the availability of fertilisers (11.2%) followed by fodder/cattle feed (10.8%) and rental agricultural machinery (10.6%). Significant decline was also reported in the availability of pesticides insecticide, fungicide etc. 9.8% and seeds (9.1944. The reasons for decline in availability of inputs were interrupt, in supply due to restrictions on movement of vehicles, closure of shops and markets etc.

All the inputs had witnessed an increase in the magnitude of prices with fodder/ cattle feed showing the highest expand of 11.6% followed by rent of Agri-machinery with an expand of 10.4%. The magnitude of increase in price was marginally less for seeds which had expanded by 8.8%. The reasons for increase in prices were disruption in supply, closure of markets and shops and decline in purchasing power of farmers as they were facing difficulty in marketing of their produce.

Impact On Farm-Gate Prices

The farm gate prices at the national level were reported to decline across all sub-sectors. The most significant decline was in the poultry sector where prices reduced as much as 17.8%. This was followed by a decrease in the prices of horticulture produce by 7.6% mainly due to its lower demand. The lowest

prices.

Decrease in magnitude of farm gate prices of commodities in agriculture and allied sectors in percentage

decline in prices was observed in the agriculture (2.2%) and pig/sheep/goat (2.9%) sectors respectively. The dairy and fisheries sector also witnessed only a moderate decline of 5.6% and 4.8%, respectively. The decline in prices could be attributed to decrease in demand for such products and interruption in movement of agriculture produce to the markets owing to ban on movement of vehicles.

Impact Of Covid-19 On Supply, Demand & Wages of Agri- Labour

The pandemic and the subsequent lockdown imposed to restrict its spread had a significant impact on the supply, demand and wages of Agri-labour through whole country. The country has also witnessed a huge number of migrant labourers trying to return back to their native places. This had a significant impact on the supply of labour in some of the states. Agricultural labour supply had shown a decline in 70% of the districts covered in the survey of NABARD. The labour supply had remained the same only in 17% of the districts and also seen an increase in 13% of the districts which may be attributed to return of migrant labour to their native places. As regards the demand for labour, at national level, the demand for labour had increased in 43% of the districts whereas it had decreased in 25% of the districts. In 32% of the districts, the demand for labour had remained the same (survey by NABARD). In the case of wages, it was reported during the survey that wage rate had increased in 41% of the districts, decreased in 13% of the districts and remained the same in 46% of the districts.

Impact On Marketing of Agricultural Products

The COVID-19 pandemic is awaited to influence agricultural markets over the next decade. OECD Scanning highlights how slower economic maturation could affect food security, farm livelihoods, greenhouse gas emissions, and trade. The size of these impacts depends, among other things, on the intensity of the drop in global GDP. Based on two scenarios for economic growth recovery, this brief describes that how the economic shock from the pandemic could reverberate through the agriculture sector over the next decade. From the falling incomes lead to a contraction in food consumption, and these effects are larger in LDCs. Some scanning and calculations shows that lower economic growth will reduce overall food consumption. Falling incomes lead to a decrease in calorie demand per capita. Projections indicate that calorie demand per capita could fall by 1% globally, compared to baseline levels, in both 2020-2021 and 2029. These impacts are amplified in least developed countries (LDCs) since those countries spend a larger share of their incomes on food. Although in utter terms of the reduction in calorie demand in LDCs is lower than any other countries, the projected percentage decline in gross calorie demand in LDCs is about two to three times higher than OECD countries 2020-21 & this impact is expected to be maintained over the medium term. Decreased consumer demand puts downward pressure on agricultural prices and production. Lower consumer demand and subsequent price decreases lead to a drop in agricultural production. Animal production is expected to decline significantly. Cereal production due to a relatively larger drop in demand for high-value products. In the short run, cereal production is projected to slightly expand in 2020-21 compared to the baseline, as lockdowns trigger supplementary demand for staple foods. Agricultural exports that slow down as a result of the pandemic on Global agricultural exports in 2020-21 have decreased 1% in volume

Change in gross calorie demand under upside and downside scenarios compared to the baseline in world, OECD and LDC countries, 2020-21 and 2029

terms comparatively with the baseline due to the decline in demand and will only partially recover over the medium term.

Impacts On Banking Sectors

In a bank dominated economy, it was conveying that specifically at a time when the stock market is touching new lows every day, the financial mediator that the most firms will turn to banks. Steps were taken by banks would be critical at addressing that economic challenge. Banks also play a major role as conventional participants in the debt market. However, it was saying that the banking sector in India is badly broken. Banks, especially the public sector banks, have been struggling to deal with ascending losses from non-performing benefit on their balance sheets. The issues in the banking sector have been hastily affecting credit growth and by the time the pandemic hit India, this difficulty had begun to injure the debt markets as well which also play an crucial role in the context of financial mediation. This could Quickly become a serious choke point as the Indian economy grapels to come in terms with this unmatched shock. It was saying that over the last few years, India has been dealing with the Twin Balance Sheet (TBS) stresses in the banking. Farmers' Access to Credit through KCC (kishan credit card) .At all- India level nearly 59% of the districts reported an adverse influence on the farmers' access to credit through KCC (kishan credit card) Although provision of banking equipment's was excepted from the limitations foisted in the lockdown yet the unfortunate influenced on KCC (kishan credit card) compensate may be due to imposed on the gesture of people, and fear of contracting covid19 through human contact and gathering. Several north-eastern states including Manipur, Mizoram and Sikkim had reported unfavourable influence in all of their districts. Other vital states reporting higher proportion of districts ostentatious unfriendly include Kerala (100%), Assam (75%), West Bengal (76%), Uttar Pradesh (75%), Bihar (73%) and Maharashtra (71%).

Impacts on banking sector

Impact on Microfinance

Large MFIs with strong, stable financial backups, in the form of lines of credit or capital commitments from financial institutions or private equity investors, were much less impacted by the pandemic than small and mid-sized MFIs, which struggled to access debt in a risk-averse market. The latter were squashed between their own commitments to their creditors and the lack of forthcoming collections on their loans to customers, until repayments started to trickle in after the lockdown was lifted in May 2020. MFIs that have a strong "phygital" (physical + digital) connection with their clients also had an advantage in navigating the crisis. They were able to find solutions that were tailored to the unique situations of their clients, for instance, by mapping repayment to cashflows, enabling them to get through the peak of the pandemic-led disruption. At the same time, digital disbursements and collections enabled these MFIs to continue to interact with their clients on an as-needed basis, even during the lockdown. MFIs that have a strong "phygital" (physical + digital) connection with their clients also had an advantage in navigating the crisis. They were able to find solutions that were tailored to the unique situations of their clients, for instance, by mapping repayment to cashflows, enabling them to get through the peak of the pandemic-led disruption. At the same time, digital disbursements and collections enabled these MFIs to continue to interact with their clients on an as-needed basis, even during the lockdown. A combination of various other factors also helped India's microfinance actor bounce back from the challenges of 2020. These include the fact that the rural customers served by the sector are among the most resilient parts of the economy, as the country deals with a tragic resurgence

of the virus, the sector will continue to depend on its resilient foundations, built in response to challenges it has learned to overcome through decades of hard experience.

Impact on MSME (impact on microfinance)

Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) are considered to be the backbone of the Indian economy as it is the second largest employment generating sector (after agriculture), employing nearly 120 million people. This sector contributes over 40% of the overall exports from India. An analysis of the impact of COVID-19 on rural economy is not complete without considering its impact on MSMEs. Crunch of Capital - SMEs in India are largely unorganized, most of the transactions carried by them are in cash which was interrupted due to lockdown and not entered properly in accounting books. In that time there were lack of cash in their hand. In the absence of accurate transaction data, these businesses do not get the mandatory credit score and find it difficult to access business loans from the formal sector.

High Cost of Transaction - Business volumes of MSMEs remain low in time of covid and hence cost of transactions remains high, both in offline and online modes of payment. This affects company's profit margin significantly in medium to long run. Cybercrime - In absence of adequate awareness and knowledge about handling digital banking and transaction activities, SMEs are found to be more vulnerable for cybercrime and phishing.

The covid-19 pandemic has a harmful sway on agriculture sector. Food safety and security were lean on due to limitations on agility interaction of people and decreased earning of people. The most exposed groups of population were influenced mostly. Therefore, the estimate taken by governments to cease the spread of the covid virus, first of all impacted negatively on global food contributions systems. The survey of literature in the burden and flexibility of agriculture structures in the face of covid-19 showed that the flexibility of food order needs to be amplified by fulfilment of technical, economic and measures. All these blueprints and compute first of all need to buffer the health and food structures security of world population.

Technical plan aiming to upgrade the functional performance level of the framework in agriculture sector are obligatory to magnify physical elasticity. Farm and institutions in agriculture sector need to grasp obligatory regaining efforts, considering the spongy, acclimatized and curative capabilities of the agricultural systems. Nevertheless, finance support and abate in face of economic overlooking of farmers permit to get better faster after Holocaust and are hailed.